

ARE PEOPLE MATERIALISTS

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Abstract: The issue of materialism challenges us to reflect on how we perceive ourselves and others in a world increasingly shaped by appearances, physical capabilities, and digital presence. As both a philosophical and social concept, materialism plays a central role in the analysis of modern society. In the context of globalization and growing consumer pressures, the question of whether people are materialistic is gaining relevance. This report presents the results of an empirical study conducted with 1,166 individuals—48% women and 51.5% men—aged between 18 and 65. The study examines contemporary attitudes toward material values and seeks to determine the extent to which people prioritize material possessions over intangible aspects of life.

Keywords: philosophy, ideals, materialism, modern society

I. INTRODUCTION

1. Problem statement

In modern society, the focus on material achievement often overshadows the importance of the non-material aspects of life. However, a number of studies and analyses prove that it is intangible factors such as personal relationships, meaning, culture, mental well-being and emotional health that play a key role in human happiness and development. [4] Erik Erikson's theory of psychosocial development places emphasis on different stages of life in which a person faces key crises and tasks shaping his identity and

long-term goals. For example, in the young age stage (intimacy vs. isolation), people focus on building meaningful relationships and long-term partnerships, which can lead to goals related to starting a family or emotional stability. In the next stage, adulthood (generativity vs. stagnation), the individual seeks to leave a mark in society through professional achievements, social contributions or the upbringing of the next generation.

This theory emphasizes that long-term goals are shaped according to social tasks and crises that a person faces in different

age periods. For example, a young person may focus their goals on career development or material well-being, while a mature individual may focus their efforts on non-material pursuits, such as contributing to society and personal growth. Thus, Erikson's theory relates long-term goals to psychosocial maturity and the person's ability to find a balance between personal ambition and social responsibility. [9]

B. F. Skinner's behavioral psychology, set forth in *The Behavior of Organisms*, explains how human behavior is formed and maintained through reinforcement (rewards and punishments). According to Skinner, long-term goals can be the result of consistent positive reinforcement that encourages certain behaviors in the direction of the desired outcome. Materialism, for example, is often associated with the pursuit of rewards such as social status or financial well-being. These goals are reinforced by external factors – such as approval from others or momentary satisfaction from the acquisition of material goods.

On the other hand, people who strive for non-material long-term goals, such as personal growth or spiritual development, may be motivated by inner reinforcement – a sense of fulfillment or meaning. Skinner's approach shows that materialistic and non-materialistic goals are the result

of different types of reinforcement that shape people's behavioral patterns over time. Those who choose materialistic aspirations often respond to quicker and more specific rewards, while people with non-material goals seek longer-term and inner satisfaction. [10] By combining these theories, we can conclude that materialism and people's long-term goals are determined by a combination of external rewards, internal aspirations, and the stage of personal development. While material goals often respond to immediate needs and external success, intangible goals related to self-realization and flow offer deeper and more lasting satisfaction. Ultimately, the balance between material and intangible is key to achieving long-term happiness and a meaningful life. As Martin Seligman, the founder of positive psychology, points out: "True happiness is not the result of material wealth, but of meaningful relationships and a fulfilling existence." [8] Here we look at the meaning of intangible things through the prism of proven research and authoritative sources. The aim is to show that despite the seeming dominance of the material, intangible values are the basis of sustainable happiness and social well-being.

Studies in the field of psychology emphasize that intangible values such as love, friendship and a sense of meaning

are essential for human happiness. One of the best known studies in this field is the Harvard University Adult Development Study, which has been going on for over 80 years and covering the lives of hundreds of participants. The results clearly show that the quality of relationships has the strongest impact on physical and mental health. "Good relationships make us healthier and happier. Loneliness kills, and close relationships protect both mind and body." – Robert Waldinger, head of the study. Research proves that people with stronger social ties live longer, experience less pain, and enjoy better mental health.

Martin Seligman, in his book "Authentic Happiness", emphasizes the importance of intangible things such as gratitude, commitment and meaning. According to him, lasting happiness is not based on material success, but on inner satisfaction. [6]

"A sense of meaning and contribution to something greater than ourselves is one of the strongest sources of satisfaction" [8]

A study by Edward Deener also supports these claims, finding that focusing on the non-material aspects of life, such as gratitude and empathy, significantly increases an individual's subjective well-being. [1]

According to UNESCO, intangible cultural heritage, including customs,

traditions, folklore, language and arts, is a major factor in the creation of social identity and cohesion. The document "Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage" [5] states:

"Intangible cultural heritage is what keeps our cultures alive and connects us to our ancestors and future generations." Studies have shown that cultural identity plays an essential role in individuals' mental well-being, creating a sense of belonging and security in a globalized world.

A 2019 report by the World Health Organization (WHO) found that art and cultural activities can significantly improve mental health by reducing stress and anxiety levels. Participation in the arts also promotes social integration and the building of stronger communities.

"Culture is not just a supplement to life, it is the basis of well-being and social progress" – WHO Report, 2019. A study by Tim Kasser, author of "The High Price of Materialism", proves that people who place too much importance on material possessions often experience lower life satisfaction, depression and anxiety. [2]

The OECD (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development) report "How's Life? Measuring Well-being" [3] shows that intangible factors such as work-life balance, access to social support and a healthy environment are crucial for quality of life. Motivation for success is a

foundational theme that touches on both individual achievement and the broader social and professional dimensions of life. Different authors and researchers look at motivation from different perspectives, with an emphasis on personal development, the psychology of success, and practical strategies for achieving results.

II. Methodology

2.1. 1.Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study is to investigate to what extent people are materialistic.

3.1.2. Research methods

To realize the objectives of the study, the general scientific method "Survey" was used. The following research techniques were also used for the purposes of the method:

- Create a survey;
- Organization of the survey: The survey was developed on Google Forms and distributed on the Internet in November 2024.

3.1.3. Subjects examined

On the basis of the respondents, **1166** people took part in the survey - 48% women; 51.5% men. The age range of the surveyed persons is from 18 to 65 years of age.

4. Results of the study

Question No. 1: What makes you happy at this stage in life? (see Fig.1) 62.4% of

the surveyed persons indicated the health of everyone in the family as the most important. 20.2% indicated financial stability. 15.6% indicated successful career development as the most important factor for happiness. 1.7% chose their own home as the answer.

And four questions on demographic characteristics (age, gender, location, education)

To Question No. 2: How important is the possession of material possessions to you?

With this question, our goal was to find out what are the priorities of people that make them happy at the moment. The conclusion from the presented results is that for the majority of the subjects studied, the most important factor for happiness is family health. Financial stability ranks second according to the respondents, while successful career development and owning a home are less significant. This proves to us that the main priority for people is the well-being of

loved ones, which prevails over material and professional aspects.

To the second question, 78.1% of the surveyed persons believe that the possession of material items is moderately important. For 11.1% of them it is very important, while 10.8% define it as unimportant.

Fig.2

Here we aimed to understand the attitudes of the studied persons towards material things and how much importance they attach to them.

Our answers show an interesting trend regarding people's attitudes towards material things. The overwhelming majority of respondents believe that material values are not a top priority, but they are also not underestimated. At the same time, a small part of the participants define the possession of material items as very important. This group probably places more importance on the security and comfort that things can provide, or the social status associated with them. On the other hand, the smallest part of the surveyed people believe that material

items are of little importance. This may indicate a focus on the non-material aspects of life, such as relationships, experiences, or spiritual values.

Question No. 3: What is the significance of intangible things for you?

The survey shows 63.3% of respondents define intangible things as very important. 32.2% of the participants believe that intangible things are moderately important, and a small part of the respondents 4.5% consider them not very important.

Fig.3

The largest share of the surveyed individuals define intangible things as very important, which emphasizes the importance of intangible aspects, such as relationships, experiences and personal development. A smaller proportion of participants have a balanced approach between tangible and non-tangible priorities. A very small part of the respondents consider them not very important, which may reflect different personal or cultural attitudes.

To Question No. 4: What is your motivation to achieve success?

70.2% of the surveyed individuals show that material prosperity and personal

satisfaction are the most important. On the other hand, 24.3% have decided that the motivation for achieving success is personal satisfaction. And the remaining 5.6% put material prosperity first.

Fig.4

With this question, we explore people's priorities and values in terms of success, looking at the balance between material and non-material aspects.

These results show that most people perceive success as a combination of external and internal factors. Material well-being is important, but it is not enough to achieve true satisfaction. People who focus solely on personal satisfaction are likely to value emotional well-being, relationships with others, and inner balance more. A small percentage that focuses only on material success may reflect differences in the value system or cultural environment.

To the fifth question, 73% of the surveyed people choose "quality-price ratio". 17.5% choose high quality regardless of the price, and only 9.5% of the respondents choose budget options.

Fig.5

The conclusion of the survey shows that the attitude towards materialism is balanced. Most people strive for practicality and rationality, choosing items that combine good quality and affordable price. This suggests a moderate approach to material values, in which people appreciate their functionality and value. On the sixth question, 65.1% of the surveyed persons remain indifferent, 25.6% feel admiration for other people's wealth, and 9.3% feel pressure and envy.

Fig.6

With this question, we aimed to understand how people react when they see others with more expensive things or greater wealth.

Based on the results obtained, we can conclude that people's attitude towards the wealth of others is quite uniform in this, the prevailing opinion is that most people do not really care do not care much about

the material possessions of others. This suggests that modern societies are increasingly focused on intangible values rather than personal relationships, experiences and self-development.

Question 7: What are your long-term goals in life?

72.5% of the respondents indicated a mixture of investments in experiences and material goods, 21.8% chose the investment in experiences, and 5.7% the accumulation of material goods.

Fig.7

As a result of the results obtained, we can conclude that modern people have a more balanced attitude towards their long-term goals. Although material well-being is still important to many people, an increasing number of people are realizing that happiness is not achieved through material possessions alone. Investments in experiences, personal relationships and skills development also play a significant role in building a satisfying life. With regard to the goals that a larger number of respondents see in the long term in front of them, it is difficult to establish whether they are materialistic or not. Rather, we focused on the percentage ratio between

the choice of material goods and experiences, which, in our opinion, tilts the scales in a positive direction, namely not materiality.

To Question No. 8: How do you react when you can't afford something you want? 73.4% of the surveyed individuals are ready to achieve their desires at a later stage. 14.6% feel dissatisfied, and as many as 12% find that it does not affect them much.

Fig.8

With this question, we aimed to understand what are the attitudes and ways with which people deal with restrictions.

When people cannot afford something they want, most prefer to be patient and fulfill their desires at a later stage, when conditions allow it. At the same time, there are those for whom such situations do not have a significant impact on their emotional state or attitudes.

The conclusion we can draw about people's materialism is that the attitude towards material desires and the ability to achieve them vary according to individual

attitudes. For some people, material acquisitions are extremely important, and the inability to realize them immediately leads to dissatisfaction. This reaction shows a stronger dependence on the material. For others, however, the achievement of desires may wait, indicating a more moderate attitude towards materialism and a better capacity for self-control. The third group, which remained emotionally unaffected, demonstrated the least dependence on material goods, which implied a lesser influence of materialism on their lives.

Question No. 9: How often do you buy things that you don't need?

67.2% of the surveyed individuals decide that they sometimes need to buy new items that they do not need. 16.8% never buy unnecessary items and 16% answered that they often resort to buying unnecessary items.

Fig.9

The conclusion we can draw is that their attitude towards owning things and the tendency to impulsive purchases reveals different levels of materialism. People who often buy unnecessary things

show a stronger attachment to material goods and a susceptibility to consumerist attitudes. At the same time, those who avoid such purchases demonstrate discipline and practicality, which implies a lesser influence of materialism in their lives. The third group, which sometimes makes unnecessary purchases, shows a moderate balance between practicality and impulsiveness, which reflects a more moderate attitude towards material possessions.

To Question No. 10: What brings you pleasure in life?

87.4% of the surveyed individuals chose "experiences and moments with loved ones", 6.8% chose "prestige in society" and the least chosen answer of the surveyed persons is 5.8%, which is "the acquisition of new things".

Fig.10

From the results obtained, we can conclude that materialism among modern people is decreasing, with a transition to more intangible values. More and more people are beginning to value quality relationships and shared experiences that

cannot be bought, instead of focusing on material acquisitions and social status. This change implies a tendency to rethink values and seek long-lasting happiness in the spiritual and emotional, rather than in the short-term satisfaction of possessions.

To Question No. 11: How important is it to you how you look in society?

56% chose "it only matters in certain situations", 32.6% chose "very important because the first impression leaves a mark" and the least chosen answer of the people surveyed was 11.9% who chose "I don't pay much attention to my appearance".

Fig.11

With this question, we aim to understand to what extent a person focuses on his appearance and social status, which can be an indicator of his materialism.

From the analysis of the results, we can conclude that appearance is important for most people, but mainly in certain situations, such as making a good first impression. This shows a balanced approach, in which people are aware of the importance of appearance for social interaction, but do not make it a top

priority. The fact that a small part of the participants completely neglect their appearance suggests that this aspect is not without importance, but for most people it is not a leading one. This can be interpreted as a sign that the subjects studied are not highly materialistic and attach more importance to other, more intangible values, such as the content of relationships and personal qualities.

And four questions on demographic characteristics (age, gender, location, education)

To the question "Which age group do you belong to?" 96.3% are from 18-25 years old. , 2.8% are from 26-40 years old. and 0.9% are 41-65 years old.

Fig.12

When asked about the gender of the respondents, 51.5% are men and 48.5% are women.

Fig.13

When asked about the settlement from which the respondents are from, 53.2% are from a large city, 14.8% are from a medium-sized city, 17.3% are from a smaller city, 10.8% are from a city of less than 30,000 people and 3.9% are from a village.

Вие сте от град между
1 166 отговора

Fig.14

To the question "What completed education do you have?" 71.4% of the respondents have secondary education, 17.1% have higher education, 10.1% have primary education and 1.4% have no education.

С какво завършено образование сте?
1 166 отговора

III. Conclusion

As a result of the empirical research on the topic "Are people materialists?", we were able to get a comprehensive picture of people's attitudes and understandings regarding materialism.

The survey data showed a variety in the participants' attitudes towards material goods – while for some people they are the main source of security and satisfaction, others perceive them as a means rather than an end in life. Our research confirmed these dependencies, but also highlighted the importance of individual differences and personal choices. At the end of our empirical research, based on the answers given by all respondents, we can conclude that modern people are faced with an internal dilemma between the material and the intangible, increasingly rethinking their priorities. On the one hand, material values such as possessions, appearance and social status still have an impact and for many remain a symbol of success and recognition. People often strive to look good and maintain a certain level of material comfort because they believe that this is the way to achieve acceptance and respect. On the other hand, there is a clearly growing awareness of the value of intangible things – quality relationships, shared experiences and inner satisfaction. Many people understand that material gains can only bring short-term joy, while the non-material aspects of life—such as

love, friendship, and personal growth—bring long-lasting happiness and meaning. It is in situations of limited opportunities or dissatisfaction with material things that people increasingly turn to these deeper and more lasting sources of joy.

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